

RI-VIS D4.1 Revision of ARIA for RI-VIS

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Description of deliverable	Revision of ARIA to accommodate the needs of RI and stakeholders to access information to identify partnering

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Executive Summary

Access to Research Infrastructure Administration (ARIA) software is already in use across a number of European Research Infrastructures. Through ARIA, a number of community tools are available for research infrastructures, their nodes, projects, facilities and communities. An audit of ARIA functionality was performed to identify the existing functionality which presented opportunities for the RI-VIS project. This audit identified areas where developments of the software could produce new or improved tools and features for addressing RI-VIS stakeholder groups and meeting the needs of the RI-VIS work program. Following this audit, the content management tools were prioritised for development, and an improved content management system was built. The new content management system uniquely integrates data sources from ARIA including news, events and calls in the first instance through application programming interfaces (APIs). The new content management system provides a more intuitive interface for editing content and allows the rapid creation of mobile friendly websites for new and existing communities.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

Access to Research Infrastructure Administration (ARIA) software

ARIA is a suite of software solutions for Research Infrastructures developed by Instruct-ERIC, the European Research Infrastructure for Structural Biology. ARIA was initially conceived as an online tool to handle the submission and peer review of research proposals for access to Instruct infrastructure. Through the CORBEL project [1], ARIA was developed to enable the management of complex proposals requiring access to multiple research infrastructures in the life science domain [2]. During this work, requirements emerged from infrastructures participating in CORBEL which helped Instruct-ERIC to further enhance the software to accommodate the needs of a broader range of infrastructures. ARIA functionality has expanded beyond access management to include a range of other services used in research infrastructures and projects across Europe and beyond, making it a one-stop-shop for management of research infrastructure. ARIA services include access management (submission of research proposals, peer review, service/technology access visits, access reporting), community management (jobs, events, news, internal messaging, networks, forums, surveys, mailshots), facility management (booking calendars, user training record) and data management (API, document hosting).

RI-VIS aims to increase the visibility of research infrastructures and through work package 4 has performed an audit of ARIA functionality to identify the features most relevant to community development, communication and information-exchange. By identifying these features and identifying needs which were not met by the software in its original form, a development plan was established and implemented to improve functionality offered for community management by revising the content management system used to create websites in ARIA such as the RI-VIS project website.

Description of work

Review of existing ARIA functionality

The first step was to review the functionality already present in ARIA as a basis for identifying opportunities for improvements or new functionality which would align with the RI-VIS project aims. The results of this review are shown in Table 1. The right-hand column of the table provides a “wish-list” for features and improvements which were then prioritised and selected for development following input from research infrastructure staff and web analytics from the RI-VIS website.

Table 1: Details of previous ARIA functionality and qualitative assessment of applicability to RI-VIS project aims and opportunities for improvements or new features aligned with these aims.

ARIA Feature	Description of functionality	Applicability to RI-VIS	Suggested improvements /enhancements
Access	Selection of services and funding source and subsequent construction of application form. Peer review of application. Management online of service provision if granted.	Not particularly applicable to RI-VIS but integration with ARIA Access management if in use in individual RIs is useful.	
Content Management System	Generation of custom webpages. Page layout can be controlled via moving resizable drag-and-drop elements onto a page. Functional	Used for the majority of pages in the RI-VIS website which are not automatically generated. Allows the	Wiki-style pages which allow the creation and updating of working

	blocks can be added into these layout elements e.g. a WYSIWIG HTML editor block or a twitter feed block.	management of website content by a wide range of administrators.	documents. Comments block in CMS to have a thread for discussing the current page content. Existing content management administration is not very user friendly and has many bugs. CMS pages should be more mobile friendly.
Client Relationship Management	Batch sending emails to groups of users affiliated with a project, or who have consented to a particular mailing list. Currently only users registered in ARIA can be contacted in this way. Emails can have custom styling to match a particular brand.	Could potentially be useful but requiring creation of an ARIA account to join a mailing list may discourage people from signing up.	Allow non-ARIA-registered users to subscribe to mailing lists. Allow network sending of CRMs
Documents	Upload, store, and download files in a folder structure. Files and folders have configurable access permissions which can allow access only to individual users or user groups.	To be used for meeting minutes, agendas and deliverable and milestone reports and any other dissemination material.	Document folders to arrange documents
Booking	Booking calendar of machines/methods can be customised to allow different users different levels of access to booking features e.g. only allow booking requests to be placed, or allow bookings of any length to be made including out-of-hours etc.	Could be used to manage use of a shared resource. Not particularly applicable to RI-VIS.	
Forums	User forums which can be public or controlled access. Only registered ARIA users can post in the forums.	Trialling use of forums for project related discussions. The usefulness of the forms depends heavily upon user adoption.	Subscribe to a forum topic for email notifications when someone posts.
Guides	Help material taggable, grouped by categories of similar guides, with target audience types and with built in feedback per guide.	Useful to assist users with ARIA features. Could potentially be used for non-ARIA help material too.	
Messages	Internal messaging with optional instant email notifications.	Not particularly applicable	
Survey	Survey form creation and sharing either with ARIA users, specified email addresses, or by anonymous participants using a link.	Useful for data collection and feedback collection for evaluation.	Surveys within network communities Ability to embed survey in CMS page
Network	Collection of ARIA features (Documents, Forums, News, Events, Jobs, Calls) for a particular community. Can have its own styling and therefore creates the feel of an independent website.	RI-VIS website is an ARIA network.	Notifications by email for join requests

News	Creation and display of news articles which are taggable	Use to promote relevant project news.	
Events	Creation and display of events which are taggable, can have registration and event start and end dates, event organiser contact form, location on map, external event link.	In use for RI-VIS and related events on the RI-VIS website.	Calendar view of events Map view of events subscribe/add event to dashboard Integrated event booking
Jobs	Creation and display of jobs which are taggable.	Increase visibility of Research Infrastructure as job creators	
Calls	Time limited, customisable application form with description and guidelines. Submitted applications can be accepted or rejected.	Used for logo competition Will be used for Staff exchange applications in WP5 task 5.3.	Community managed calls within networks
Projects	Manage mailing lists and project affiliation at registration or later from the user profile. Privacy policy defined on a project level	RI-VIS project included at ARIA registration as an option. RI-VIS privacy policy included	Integrate projects with networks

Gathering new requirements

In addition to the review of existing functionality, the RI-VIS consortium were consulted on their requirements from a web platform for information exchange. Work package 5 task 5.1 in particular provided a great deal of input into requirements. The output of task 5.1 is a Communications Standards Toolkit for Research infrastructures [3]. The nature of this resource is that it will be subject to constant change and review, and a static document form for the resource would quickly become out of date. Work package 5 agreed with the ERIC Forum implementation project to support the revision and updating of the toolkit beyond the RI-VIS project to keep it current and relevant. As such the toolkit requires a ‘home’ where it can be hosted, and the hosting platform should enable easy review and update of the content. It was agreed that ARIA could provide this platform with some additional development. A similar need was presented from the former COOP+ project who have produced another valuable resource, a communication handbook for research infrastructures [4] which the project participants wanted to continue to update as a ‘living document’.

Prioritising developments based on functionality review and requirement gathering exercise

From the functionality review and requirement gathering exercises a number of possible developments and enhancements were considered. We then prioritised these based on which would be expected to have the highest impact for communities and visibility. As a result, any proposed developments in the site forums were de-prioritised as the forums have not been used and adopted by the RI-VIS community or by the Instruct-ERIC community, with discussions tending to continue elsewhere and by email rather than on forums. Features which were requested by multiple parties were prioritised such as a system to allow comments on page so that future updates to the page can be discussed in a wiki-style way. Web analytics information also informed the prioritisation process. Events pages form the main traffic to the RI-VIS website with 28% of site visits containing a visit to an event page in the period 9 July 2019 – 8 Jan 2020. News were the second most visited page type with 12% of site visits containing a visit to a news page in the same period. As a result of the higher traffic, improving the events and news pages were prioritised over other areas such as documents which attracted only 3% of visits.

Responsive design and mobile friendliness

Mobile devices are more and more commonly used for social networking and mobile browsing. Analysis of the traffic to the RI-VIS website [5] ri-vis.eu shown in Figure 1 demonstrates that the majority (57%) of visits to the website are made via a smartphone, 41% of visits were made on a desktop computer with 2% of visits from other devices types. Interestingly Figure 2 shows that the ratio of desktop to smartphones almost reverses when it comes to the number of actions taken. An action is counted whenever a visitor visits a page, downloads a file or clicks on an external link etc. 60% of actions are performed using desktop computers compared to 39% of actions performed on a smartphone device. This could be due to a number of factors, though it could be partially explained by the fact that the current website is not optimised for mobile devices. Certain actions for example menus and navigation (e.g. the dropdown menus which open on mouse hover) are difficult to operate on mobile devices with touchscreen interfaces. As the majority of our visits are from mobile devices we should optimise the experience for this type of device, whilst not compromising the experience for desktop users who make the second largest number of website visits. To achieve this we use a method called responsive design [6], where flexible grid systems are used to adapt the layout of a page to the device screen size and orientation. Adaptive design [7] is an alternative method where a number of different designs are made and the optimal design is selected and applied based on the device screen size and orientation.

Figure 1: Devices used to visit the RI-VIS website (<https://ri-vis.eu>) in the 6 months from July 9 2019 - Jan 8 2020

Figure 2: Actions performed on the RI-VIS website by device type (<https://ri-vis.eu>) in the 6 months from July 9 2019 - Jan 8 2020

Integration of ARIA data sources with content management

ARIA functionality is broken down into a number of smaller components or modules. In earlier versions of ARIA (V1, V2) these modules were not stand-alone and had many interdependencies forming a single monolithic application. The upcoming version, for which this current work performed under RI-VIS forms a pilot, will use a revised architecture depicted in Figure 3 where the components are split into independent microservices which can each operate in isolation. Information from a microservice (e.g. news microservice, calls microservice, user microservice) can be exchanged with other microservices, or with dependent applications over Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). The front-end content management system and user facing web-pages are an example of a dependent application. Dependent applications may also be external applications i.e. those run by other organisations but using the ARIA APIs.

Figure 3: Planned ARIA architecture to integrate independent microservices with each other and the previous monolithic application via APIs.

The added value here of ARIA over other content management systems available elsewhere is in its ability to integrate research infrastructure data sources from the ARIA APIs into user-facing web pages through tailored content elements called ‘blocks’.

The new API-centric architecture also increases the interoperability of data used in ARIA with external websites and services. CatRIS, a project working to produce a common catalogue of European Research Infrastructure services [8], will be using APIs to gather and update their catalogue. This catalogue would provide a unique single portal where researchers from any discipline can locate the services on offer from European research infrastructures. The advantage of presenting data through APIs to service the content blocks is that the same endpoints can be used to interface with other applications, in this example the CatRIS catalogue. Blocks could also be developed to make use of data from APIs external to ARIA e.g. if an infrastructure provided their catalogue via an API it could be integrated into a new ARIA block and displayed on an ARIA website.

User-friendly editing interface

In addition to the new look and feel and mobile friendly design of the published website, the edit interfaces for pages and blocks were completely redone to make them more intuitive and easier to modify. A sidebar menu is available for site-wide options such as colour scheme, font, logo and site pages and navigation. When on a page in editor mode simple + buttons act as anchors to add any type of new blocks. When a page has existing blocks the position of the plus button shows where the new block will be added relative to exiting blocks. Hovering over a block will generate a bar of buttons at the top of the block to edit the block settings, move the block up or down on the page relative to other blocks, or to delete the block altogether. Clicking the block options button opens a sidebar menu for options specific to that block type. Other elements of a block such as text and images can be modified simply by clicking on the element and typing in the case of text or dragging

and dropping/ file upload in the case of an image. For text there is the ability to perform basic text formatting such as bold, italic, underline, bullets, numbered lists and hyperlinks, but the overall styling and look and feel is maintained with the overall site theme.

The simplicity of the interface should make it easier to adopt and encourage more users to have a go because there is a smaller barrier to entry when starting afresh with the system. It should take a small amount of time to create a modern website from scratch without any training. This is a great benefit for new communities adopting the system.

Conclusion/Next steps

Publish prototype

The prototype has been developed but authorisation still needs to be integrated with the ARIA Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI). When this is implemented authenticated users will have different levels of access (e.g. to edit pages and blocks) based on their roles and group membership. After this has been done the prototype described in this deliverable will go through the stages of internal testing and then deployment.

Additional blocks

More blocks will be developed using the same architecture. Examples of block types which will be developed next will be calls related blocks to use the call API to display call information and call submission forms. A comments block, and document download block will be developed to meet the requirements of the WP5 toolkit. The development of some of these new blocks will necessitate the development of new APIs and microservices e.g. documents.

Implement WP5 Communication Standards

WP5 will use the developed system to create an online version of their toolkit [3] expanding its content to include content which is not suitable for a document format e.g. links to resources, material which needs regular updating e.g. guidance on specific social media platforms.

New Communities

The new content management system can be adopted by infrastructures, projects and facilities worldwide as part of the wider suite of ARIA software services.

References

- [1] *Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services (CORBEL)*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/654248>, 2015.
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<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c04e77a8&appId=PPGMS>.

- [5] N. Haley, "RI-VIS Website Setup," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/3301924#.XIAa-S2cZhE>.
- [6] E. Marcotte, *Responsive Web Design*, New York: A Book Apart, 2011.
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Appendices

Appendix 1 – Screenshots of new functionality

Theming, pages and navigation

The screenshot displays a web application interface with a sidebar menu on the left and a main content area on the right. The sidebar menu includes a list of pages and a navigation menu. The main content area shows a message: "No blocks for page *Test page* have yet been created. Please switch to "EDIT" mode and start adding blocks."

Title	Path
Home	/
Work Packages	/work_packages
News	/news
News Item	/news/item_id
Events	/events
Event	/events/item_id
Article 1	/work_packages/art1
Test page	/test

Menu Name	Link
Home	to: /
Work Packages	to: /work_packages
News	to: /news
Events	to: /events
Test	to: /test

HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

RI-VIS

HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

No blocks for page *Test page* have yet been created.
Please switch to "EDIT" mode and start adding blocks.

New block types produced

Article preview

The image displays two screenshots of a web browser showing an article preview block in a CMS interface. The top screenshot shows the block in a light theme, and the bottom screenshot shows it in a dark theme with a sidebar of settings.

Top Screenshot (Light Theme):

- Browser address bar: localhost:3001/test
- Navigation menu: HOME, WORK PACKAGES, NEWS, EVENTS, TEST
- RI-VIS logo in the top left corner.
- Article Preview Block:
 - Image: A group of scientists in a laboratory setting.
 - Title: **Article Preview Block**
 - Description: This is a one image with caption, title and rich description text. Click inside dashed rectangles to start editing
 - Link: [READ MORE](#)
 - Caption: Caption
- Control icons: A pink circle with a plus sign (+) is positioned above the block, and another pink circle with a plus sign (+) is positioned below it.
- Bottom control bar: Three pink circular icons (a toggle, a gear, and a list icon).

Bottom Screenshot (Dark Theme):

- Browser address bar: localhost:3001/test
- Navigation menu: HOME, WORK PACKAGES, NEWS, EVENTS, TEST
- Dark theme background.
- Article Preview Block:
 - Image: A group of scientists in a laboratory setting.
 - Title: **Article Preview Block**
 - Description: This is a one image with caption, title and rich description text. Click inside dashed rectangles to start editing
 - Link: [READ MORE](#)
 - Caption: Caption
- Control icons: A pink circle with a plus sign (+) is positioned above the block, and another pink circle with a plus sign (+) is positioned below it.
- Left sidebar:
 - Dark:
 - Left to right:
 - Full Article Page:
- Top right corner: A small window control icon (maximize, close, etc.).

Article

localhost:3001/test

RI-VIS HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

Article Block

Caption

This is a one image with caption, title and rich description text. Click inside dashed rectangles to start editing

RI-VIS

Article Preview Block

News list

localhost:3001/test

RI-VIS HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

All news

News list body text

RI-VIS Spotlight on ASSEMBLE Plus Ocean Sampling Day

Genomic techniques have allowed us to characterise whole organisms and ecosystems, as well as focusing on single genes and their function. These data provide an insight to how organisms, their environments, and interactions influence the functioning ecosystems and more specifically, marine ecosystems. The ability to link organisms to their habitats enables us to gain a better and deeper understanding of how ecosystems work along with making us...

RI-VIS to exhibit at the AAAS Annual Meeting in Seattle, Feb 13-16

Genomic techniques have allowed us to characterise whole organisms and ecosystems, as well as focusing on single genes and their function. These data provide an insight to how organisms, their environments, and interactions influence the functioning ecosystems and more specifically, marine ecosystems. The ability to link organisms to their habitats enables us to gain a better and deeper understanding of how ecosystems work along with making us...

RI-VIS Spotlight on Instruct-ERIC cooperation with Latin America

Internationalisation is a key focus of many European Research Infrastructures. Instruct-ERIC, a pan-European research infrastructure in structural biology has been working closely with institutions in Latin America to form partnerships with structural biology communities across the region; aiming to train students and early career researchers from Latin American institutions through mobility, collaborative work, courses and workshops. Claudia Alén...

RI-VIS Logo Competition Winner

RI-VIS

News preview

localhost:3001/test

RI-VIS

HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

Our Latest News at a Glance

Please navigate to our news page for more

1. RI-VIS Spotlight on ASSEMBLE Plus Ocean Sampling Day
2. RI-VIS Spotlight on Instruct-ERIC cooperation with Latin America
3. RI-VIS Logo Competition Winner

⊕ ⊖

Tagged news preview

localhost:3001/test

RI-VIS

HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

Our Latest News at a Glance

Please navigate to our news page for more

1. RI-VIS Spotlight on ASSEMBLE Plus Ocean Sampling Day
2. RI-VIS Spotlight on Instruct-ERIC cooperation with Latin America
3. RI-VIS Logo Competition Winner

⊕ ⊖

Tagged News Block

Please specify the tags in block's settings

1. RI-VIS project officially launched

⊕ ⊖

News page

RI-VIS to exhibit at the AAAS Annual Meeting in Seattle, Feb 13-16

RI-VIS will have a booth at the 2020 American Association for the Advancement of Science Annual Meeting from Feb 13-16 in Seattle, WA (USA). The theme of this year's meeting is Envisioning Tomorrow's Earth. AAAS 2020 is a major international gathering, attracting thousands of scientists, engineers, policymakers, educators and journalists together to discuss the most recent developments in science and technology. This is the largest conference RI-VIS has exhibited at thus far in the project, taking place at the Washington State Convention Center. RI-VIS is a Horizon 2020-funded project to increase the visibility of European

Events list

Upcoming Events

Scroll down for more

The Third African Synchrotron Light Source Conference (AfLS3): towards a brighter future
From Nov 15th, 22:00 to Nov 20th, 21:00

The AfLS3 will be held in Kigali, Rwanda, from 16th - 21st November 2020. It will be hosted by International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP)/East Africa Institute for fundamental research (EAIFR), located at University of Rwanda (UR), college of science and technology.

The 9th Brazil School for Single Particle Cryo-EM
From Nov 5th, 03:00 to Nov 18th, 02:00

The Brazil School for Single Particle Cryo-EM is an intensive hands-on course/workshop, in which theory and practice are tightly intertwined. The spectrum of topics covered suits attendees that are new to the field as well as those for whom the technique is already of growing importance in their research and who wish to acquire an in-depth understanding of the methodology.

IUPAB 2020
From Oct 26th, 12:00 to Oct 30th, 21:00

The 20th IUPAB Congress will take place from 26 - 30 October 2020, at the Rafain Palace Hotel and Convention Centre, Brazil. This congress aims to offer a broad international overview of research frontiers and recent developments in biophysics, biochemistry, and molecular biology.

Events calendar

Events preview

Our Upcoming Events at a Glance
Please navigate to our events page for more

1. The Third African Synchrotron Light Source Conference (AFLS3):
towards a brighter future
From Nov 15th, 22:00 to Nov 20th, 21:00
2. The 9th Brazil School for Single Particle Cryo-EM
From Nov 5th, 03:00 to Nov 18th, 02:00
3. IUPAB 2020
From Oct 26th, 12:00 to Oct 30th, 21:00

Tagged event preview

Events page URL:

Max Items:

Tags:

HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

Our Upcoming Events at a Glance

Please navigate to our events page for more

1. The Third African Synchrotron Light Source Conference (AFLS3):
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3. IUPAB 2020
From Oct 26th, 12:00 to Oct 30th, 21:00

Tagged Events Block

Please specify the tags in block's settings

1. The Third African Synchrotron Light Source Conference (AFLS3): towards a brighter future
From Nov 15th, 22:00 to Nov 20th, 21:00
Kigali
2. 3rd CRIGH General Assembly (Mozambique)
From Oct 20th, 22:00 to Oct 22nd, 21:00
3. RI-VIS Africa-Europe Symposium
From Mar 22nd, 20:00 to Mar 24th, 19:00
Wolfson Pavilion and Foyer on the Health Sciences Campus of the University of Cape Town

Event page

localhost:3001/events/the-third-african-synchrotron-light-source-conference-afls3-towards-a-brighter-future

RI-VIS HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

The Third African Synchrotron Light Source Conference (AFLS3): towards a brighter future

From Nov 15th, 22:00 to Nov 20th, 21:00

**3rd African Synchrotron Light Source Conference
AFLS3 : towards a brighter future**

Kigali-Rwanda 16-21 November 2020

The AFLS3 will be held in Kigali, Rwanda, from 16th - 21st November 2020 hosted by International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP)/East Africa Institute for fundamental research (EAIFR)

<http://afls3.africanlightsource.org/>

Contact: Natalie Haley
Registration is open from: Sep 9th, 23:00 to Nov 4th, 21:00

Kigali

localhost:3001/events/the-third-african-synchrotron-light-source-conference-afls3-towards-a-brighter-future

RI-VIS HOME WORK PACKAGES NEWS EVENTS TEST

Kigali-Rwanda 16-21 November 2020

The AFLS3 will be held in Kigali, Rwanda, from 16th - 21st November 2020 hosted by International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP)/East Africa Institute for fundamental research (EAIFR)

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Contact: Natalie Haley
Registration is open from: Sep 9th, 23:00 to Nov 4th, 21:00

Kigali
Rwanda

Google Maps showing Kigali, Rwanda. Map data ©2020 Google. Terms of Use

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